

GENERAL ABSORBING OF "PROFESSIONAL PSYCHOLOGY" AND REFLECTIONS ABOUT PSYCHOGRAM, PROFESSIONOGRAM AND PROFESSIONOGRAPHY

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Abstract. *This article is provided with the conditions for the emergence of professional psychology, its subject, goals and tasks, the classification of scientific research methods, the analysis of scientific approaches to the surface of psychogram, professionogram and professionography, views on the natural and social factors that affect the mental development of a person.*

Keywords: *the main goal of professional psychology, psychogram, professionogram and professionography, informative, diagnostic, prognostic, methodical.*

ОБЩЕЕ УСВОЕНИЕ "ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПСИХОЛОГИИ" И РАЗМЫШЛЕНИЯ О ПСИХОГРАММЕ, ПРОФЕССИОГРАММЕ И ПРОФЕССИОГРАФИИ

Аннотация. *В статье приводятся условия возникновения профессиональной психологии, ее предмет, цели и задачи, классификация методов научного исследования, анализ научных подходов к поверхности психограммы, профессиограммы и профессиографии, взгляды на природные и социальные факторы, которые влияют на психическое развитие человека.*

Ключевые слова: *основная цель профессиональной психологии, психограмма, профессиограмма и профессиография, информативная, диагностическая, прогностическая, методическая.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the main task of professional psychology and the fields of activity in the social system is the person who is the main subject, including professional activity, the processes of knowledge and understanding of the world, the emotional and volitional sphere, the research of specific typological characteristics, factors affecting the activity system, to analyze the secrets of professional skills, to implement the most effective methods of managing the field of activity. The main goal of the "Professional Psychology" course is the needs of society in relation to the specialties chosen by future professionals, the content of professional activity in various fields, the psychological demands of the profession on a person (professionogram), the psychological capabilities of a person in relation to professional activity (psychogram), work conditions, suitability of the chosen profession to a person's interests and needs, requirements for the owner of the profession, professional ethics, qualifications, psychological nature of the professional direction, various areas of specialization and their specific aspects. At the same time, to help students understand the psychological essence of their chosen profession and its importance to society based on the ideas of national ideology, professional etiquette, professional ethics, the complex aspects of the chosen profession from the point of view of stable values and moral criteria in society; to analyze from the point of view, to determine the principles of loyalty to the

profession; informing future professionals about the psychological and pedagogical technologies of mastering the secrets of professional skills, introducing them to the basics of professional activity motivation, professional promotion and counseling. The role of "Professional psychology" is considered as one of the most important factors in helping the future professional to understand the social basis of professional activity and to master professional communication based on the individual-psychological characteristics of the future profession.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In professionography, the objects that make up the labor process, the subject of labor, the tasks, tools and conditions of the subject of labor are studied. One of the main principles of professionography is the principle of a differential (separate) approach to the study of professional activity. For example, for vocational counseling and vocational selection, it is necessary to distinguish vocationally important signs, which should be differentiated according to the vocational ability of the test takers. The results of professionography are reflected in the professionogram, which includes a description of working conditions, rights and obligations of the employee, important professional qualities, as well as instructions about his health. An important component of the professionogram is the psychogram, which is a description of the motivated, volitional and emotional sphere of the specialist. A psychogram is a psychological portrait of a person, which shows a group of mental functions necessary for the profession. Various methods are used in professionography:

- social methods (questionnaires, observation with questions);
- psychological methods (interview, observational experience, personal questionnaires, tests, experiments, biographies, methods of studying the product of activity);
- physiological methods (ECG, ultrasound, MRI, measurement of arterial pressure, anthropometric data);
- impact of technological processes and other methods.

RESULTS

E.M. Ivanova offered 4 groups of professions:

- informative;
- diagnostic;
- prognostic;
- methodical.

Informative professionography - octants, that is, profession professional counseling work with persons facing the need to make a choice intended for, including students, educational institutions admission of graduates, unemployed and those who want to change their profession possible. Informative professional works, special professional literature through familiarization with, analysis and study of documents is increased.

Diagnostic (diagnostic) professionalization - work low efficiency, product quality at the required level such as absence, accident, injury, lack of personnel conducted to determine the reasons.

Diagnostic professionography includes the following issues:

Content of activity:

- labor subject and issues;
- requirements for the quality of work results.

Working tools:

- type and procedure of work;
- management bodies;
- workplace organization.

Activity of the labor subject:

- types of actions and their description;
- work planning and execution control;
- factors interfering with professional activity;
- errors and injuries occurring during work;
- personal and psychophysiological qualities of the labor subject requirements;
- diagnosis of low efficiency of the work subject;
- practical examination on improvement of professional activity.
- Collection of empirical data in diagnostic professionography is done.

Prognostic professionography - to improve professional activity is used in order to make recommendations aimed at:

- general description of the profession;
- development history and prospects of the profession;
- socio-economic conditions of professional activity;
- professional environment;
- content of profession;
- factors determining professional knowledge;
- development of professional knowledge;
- level of professional education and professional development;
- professional training;
- professional inclination of the employee;
- level of qualifications;
- possibility to change specialty and profession;
- assessment of career prospects;
- professional opportunities of the person;
- professional activity of the employee.

Genetics, modeling in prognostic professionalization professional requirements and psychophysiological of the person through experimental methods capabilities are compared.

Methodical professionalization of the work subject to the psychologist development of methods of learning the status and important professional qualities allows. Methodical according to the purpose and tasks of the research the pattern of professionalization will also change. For example, professional work and due to rest routine, occupational exhaustion and fatigue the effect of a decrease in efficiency, an indifferent attitude to one's work.

This chart is used for learning:

- The content of the activity of the labor subject:
 1. Type of actions and their description.
 2. Nature of work planning and execution.
 3. Emotional states.
 4. Types of workplace discomfort.

5. Errors and injuries that appear during the activity.

- Working conditions:

1. Sanitation and hygiene (air temperature, dust, humidity, etc.).

2. Light level, noise.

3. Work order.

4. Form of payment and incentives.

Studying the professional skills of a specialist the following diagram of professionography is used:

- Activity content:

1. Requirements for the qualifications of workers (professional knowledge, skills and abilities, will qualities and abilities).

2. Rights and obligations of workers.

- Labor organization:

1. Training.

2. Professional backup options.

3. Creative skills.

- Activity of the labor entity:

1. Type of actions and their description.

2. Work planning and control.

3. Individual characteristics of activity.

DISCUSSION

Professions and general description of his specialties is called professionography. The result of professionography is a professionogram, it can put the specializations in a person, a group of people are generalized descriptions based on their requirements. A part of the professionogram is a psychological professionogram, the rest - requirements for the human psyche, such as a list of professional skills. Professions includes classification, which is expressed by various criteria: technological, hygienic, psychological, etc. Any profession study and description have a specific purpose.

Professional programs focus on the following tasks:

- justification of personnel's readiness for labor activity;
- taking into account hygienic conditions and improving the environment strain;
- justification of professional advice and professional choice;
- setting standards of labor activity;
- assessment of labor safety measures.

CONCLUSIONS

Occupational medicine, labor with scientific research of labor such sciences as physiology, labor psychology are involved. All studies in the field of psychology, first of all, a specific profession. It starts with studying the activity. Modern science and technology development, new modern technologies in all fields in connection with the introduction into practice, labor activity not only the conditions, but also the content of work is changing.

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